

The Role of the Skin Microbiome in Atopic Dermatitis

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Abstract

Skin microbiota play a critical role in human and health sickness, such as the processes that underpin development of atopic dermatitis. This review offers researches concerned with the primary focus of microorganisms in skin disease and delineates dysbiosis based on the disease's pathology. This review also discusses interventions that target the skin microbiota and summarises the relevant literature implications for skin microbiome research. Therefore, the nature of the present review show that more investigations describing the effects of Staphylococcal species on skin diseases may contribute to design new targets for atopic dermatitis and others similar ailments in the future. Moreover, it revealed that there is recognition of the host and microbiome interconnectivity in health and skin homeostasis in the literature. Among the numerous extrinsic and intrinsic factors that disrupt skin microbiota there are many that eventually lead to the development of skin diseases. Imbalance or derangement of a normal microbial skin flora referred to as dysbiosis is evident in atopic dermatitis. The skin is responsive in that it must work as a shield between it and the rest of the world and actively counter act the mechanical and chemical forces most of the time manifested on the skins surface. These lead to changes in their environment in terms of pH, sebum content, water content and skin co-efficient of sweating non specific immunity. Host genetics with environment, commensal organisms and allergens are barriers that must be studied and unmask the pathophysiology of atopic dermatitis and therapeutic management for this disease. Dysbiosis has even been described as a disruption in skin microbiome; over the past decade technology and cost has enabled exploration of the skin and microbiota.

Introduction

Atopic dermatitis is an epidemic skin disorder that is present in people of different parts of the world and is not limited to the developed nations. Such condition strongly affects the emotional and psychological state of a person, and has an enormous impact on the mood and psychological conditions of a person. You might think or believe that the root causes of atopic dermatitis are many and varied yet this disease's actual origins remain somewhat mysterious. It consists of many components, including genetic factors that make up for increased risk for developing it, immunologic disturbances and acting environmental factors that include infectious agents and presence of microbiota.

Almost exclusively, atopic dermatitis shows itself in childhood and equally persists in adolescence and adulthood thus affecting the quality of such a person's life during these crucial developmental stages. Since this affliction is present in a significant number of children, especially ranging from 20-30% of cases, and at least 10% of adults in the western world, there is a need to understand the specific relations of each of the etiologic factors and this disease. Such understanding can, therefore, help in early prevention and management of this common and costly illness [1-3]. Atopic dermatitis is a chronic skin disease of repeated relapsing nature involving possible systemic manifestation, with chronic pruritus and inflammation of the skin. It is a disease that is experienced by people of all ages and is determined by inherited factors as well

More Information

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as other determinant factors. The skin is one of the largest organs and has a major job of shielding the body from several factors that range from injury, irritation and infection. Furthermore, it provides warmth conservation means, the regulation of its temperature, fluid homeostasis, as well as the presence of immunologic dendritic cells.

Health of the skin is directly dependent upon the rest of the body since the skin illustrates the connections between the various systems and organs. Indeed, the skin health can be regarded as a mirror reflecting a given person health and including physical, immunological, psychological, and even social aspects. The skin which is the largest organ of the body surfaces exposes a wide area offering ground for host of microorganisms such as bacteria, fungi, viruses and mites. Such organisms nevertheless coexist in harmony with the host organism creating what is termed skin microbiome.

The skin microbiome also differs with the physique or the zone of the host together with their eating habits. For instance, microorganisms that exist on the face might be very different from those exposed to on the arms or the legs. Additionally, the skin microbiome may be different in people who live in two different locations or those who perform particular tasks. This as you will see shows that the skin microbiome is more fluid and is capable of changing depending on the environment.

The skin microbiome is not only in contact with its surrounding environment but it also actively influences the skin. It is a symbiotic component of the human holobiont and positively contributes the general homeostasis and health of the man. The microbes living on and in the skin host various beneficial effects for the skin, guarding against pathogenic microorganisms, as well as carrying out physiological activities. , the host provides nutrients needed to support the microorganisms, keeps the numbers of bacterial antagonists, or bacteriophages, in check and an open access to the exterior for skin colonization by the microorganisms.

In conclusion, skin and skin microbiota are intertwined with one another in the healthy body balance and the presented data outline the number of factors involved in this process. In order to formulate goals and targets for treating skin diseases including atopic dermatitis, it is necessary to comprehend the multifaceted relationships of the skin organism and factors of its environment. The knowledge about the skin microbiome and its potential for contribution to human health is still in a development stage and as soon as more data is collected for further research, it is anticipated that we will learn more about this unseen skin world [4-8].

Definition and Prevalence

Atopic dermatitis (AD) is a form of chronic, relapsing, and pruritic skin disease of known complex genetic predisposition. It is also classified as complex because patients have indicated that both environmental and genetic factors contribute to the disease. Atopic dermatitis is confirmed internationally with an approximate prevalence ranging from 2.5% for adults to 10% – 20 % for children. Scientists estimate that about 2-3% of adults are infected and there is over 10% of children positive with the disease. These totals translate into an estimated 20 million patients in Europe and 31 million in North America suffering from the chronic form of the disease. Those who develop early onset are children for more than 20% of infants in industrialized nation may have initial sign of AD. Atopic dermatitis onset occurs in the first 3 years of life and nearly 80% of affected children will outgrow it in childhood. As a chronic skin condition, atopic dermatitis is neither distributed homogeneously in populations globally, but its prevalence differs substantially between different regions and ranges between 15-50% [9-10].

Environmental factors; stress; family history; nutrition; immunologic scores; skin barrier function abnormalities and infection have also been described to play a causative role for atopic dermatitis. Such critical external conditions as seasonality and climate variations, humidity, water hardness, etc. are the most significant. Moreover, TS has also been found to lower skin lipids and modify skin barrier integrity. Another relevant, albeit recognised modifiable, risk factor is that of genetic heritability. The prevalence of AD in first-degree relatives is much higher, and directly to identify it, more than the 40% of children of AD have parents with AD history, so the elevated risk for atopy is distinguishable for such children. Hence, a great deal of emphasis is placed on identifying early signs and symptoms of AD, as missed or incorrect diagnostic results can result in exposure to inadequate therapy, deterioration of the patient's quality of life as well as that of their relatives, and psychological tension. AD covers many forms of the illness, from the most common atopic eczema to contact eczema and endogenous eczema. Thus, if a patient has AD, he/she also often has other conditions associated with it in a manner that demonstrates their symptoms. The part played by the community, the physician and the general practitioner should of course be underlined to try and keep the affected people as close to the symptom free as is possible [11-13].

Clinical Manifestations

Atopic dermatitis (AD) affects mainly the skin, with five characteristic features: Pruritus, eczema, dryness or desquamation, weeping or exudation and lichenification. The features of exudation, dryness, and

lichenification are most characteristic in chronic stage of AD. Vesicle formation is observed to be more common in early onset Alzheimer's disease while papules are most frequently reported in children of up to 16 years. Other common clinical patterns are oozing, weeping, ear-nose-throat skin involvement and early periorbital dermatitis in AD. It is apparent that clinical features of AD can be variable intra and extra individually and that cutaneous disease can present in different ways in different ages.

This paper has looked at skin manifestations in AD focusing on skin dryness which is accompanied by pruritus, relapses as well as skin infections due to the breach of the skin barrier by AD. AD has a progressive nature with a variety of clinical manifestations in the form of clinical signs and symptoms, physical discomfort and psychological disorders in patients and in families. In addition, the course of the disease can be accompanied by such allergic diseases as allergic rhinitis, asthma, and food allergy – the atopic march. Because of all the aforesaid factors, the clinical appearance of the skin is often the primary reason an individual espouses with the healthcare system [15].

But compliance with topical therapy, in particular, is even worse than compliance with the systemic drugs therapy. This means that lack of compliance can even worsen the intensity of the already manifested symptoms and increase the time the patient has to spend with AD. So it becomes imperative for healthcare providers to try and exert their best effort in achieving optimal clinical care and the sign and symptom of AD as minimal as possible. [16] (4) exudation; and (5) lichenification. The exudation, dryness, and lichenification mainly occur in the chronic phase of AD. Vesicle formation is seen more in early-onset AD, whereas papules show a peak prevalence up to the age of 16. Other common features include oozing, weeping, ear-nose-throat, and periorbital skin involvement in early AD. It is widely recognized that the clinical manifestations of AD can vary in individuals and on different body areas, as well as presenting differently at various times of life [14].

In summary, AD presents with skin dryness, often associated with pruritus, relapses, and skin infections due to the loss of the skin barrier. AD has a chronic course accompanied by a variety of clinical symptoms, physical discomfort, and the psychological distress of the patients and their families. Furthermore, the course of the disease can often be complicated by concomitant allergic rhinitis, asthma, or food allergy, the so-called atopic march. For all the reasons described above, the clinical appearance of the skin is usually the main reason for consulting the healthcare system [15].

Compliance with topical therapy, however, has even lower adherence than therapy with systemic drugs. This lack of adherence can further exacerbate the

symptoms and prolong the duration of AD. Therefore, it is crucial for healthcare providers to focus on promoting optimal clinical management and reducing the signs and symptoms of AD as low as possible [16].

They use of regimes such as the application of emollients and moisturizers to soften the skin, topical corticosteroids to minimize inflammation and immunomodulators to help balance the immune system. Moreover, the reduction in contact with their aggravating factors like fabrics, chemicals, or foods is also a major driving force to the management of AD [17].

In the past few years, there has been an evolution in using targeted treatments of AD; for instance, the use of biologic drugs that target various pro-inflammatory molecules. These therapies provide new hope for the patients with severe or refractory AD who did not benefit from other medications. However, the reader must bear in mind that such treatments may sometimes be slightly dangerous and must therefore be used under the supervision of a physician [18].

Thus, the management of AD was revealed to be multifaceted and needs individual approach because of the disease's complexity. Given proper education, encouragement, and appropriate adherence to medication regimens, patient diagnosed with Alzheimer's disease can experience a better regulation of their symptoms, as well as overall quality of life. Current and future research and developments of dermatology present new knowledge and treatment ideas that can be used to address patients with AD [18].

The Skin Microbiome

Skin Microbiome

The human skin is not a static structure; it is rather a place where a rich diversity of microorganisms lives and are called skin microbiota. Originally, there was an assumption of the skin microbial community was formed only from bacteria although in fact it also contains different types of fungi and viruses. That is, the bacterial population of a healthy skin is one which the skin harbors a large number of species belonging to different taxa, so that the different bacterial species can in turn modify the skin's characteristics in some way. This importance is illustrated by considering the effects of microbiota depletion, or the use of animals with germ-free phenotypes, and the role of microbiota in modulating many aspects of physiology and disease. While most of such microorganisms stimulate an immunological reaction, that activity is regulated by the commensal microorganisms. Therefore, the immune responses are either are never generated in the first place, when for example, a threat posed by a particular pathogen is eliminated by a commensal organism or are generated on a much larger scale to either the pathogen or the commensal organisms that managed to alert the immune system in the first place. Healthy

skin microbiome also supports skins protective functions because the skin microbiome occupies location in the skin surface that would otherwise be colonized by pathogens and deny them an environment to grow [19-21].

Besides a balanced skin microbiome, many microbial aspects can affect skin function in a positive way. Either nutrients & toxins or any other biochemical in the human body will help in making the current status of skin microbiome. Membranes of nutrients, toxins, or any other skin microbiome metabolite or byproduct membranes can interact and can be transported into our bodies via immune cell activation which will be further discussed. Many factors contribute to the current composition of the skin microbiome: those throughout the body like age, sex, and diet, other contributors which are related to skin biology at the regional level including humidity, cells of the immune system, and impact of death on skin microbes. Moreover, cleaning and any contact with it—natural rubbing with skin oils, sweat or protective moisturizers, etc—may interfere with skin microbiota. Synergy between host keratinocytes and an active ecological niche defines a large and highly active community of bacteria, viruses, and fungi which calibrate a complex and overall mutually beneficial orchestra. While hosts and their microbiota may occasionally communicate to alleviate one stress or to vie for an essential nutrient or to produce substances toxic to the other, these microbes live symbiotically with the host skin cells in what seems to be a win-win situation [21-22]

Definition and Composition

The Skin Microbiome: Definition and Composition Skin microbiota refers to a population of microorganisms including microbes of bacteria, archaea, fungi, eukaryotic and prokaryotic viruses distancing along the human skin where each of the microbes thrives in different microsites throughout the body and exists in symbiosis with the skin host. Human skin microbiota is as diverse as any of the other human body niches, for example, gastrointestinal tract or the respiratory system. However, similar to the gut, skin microbiota evolved symbiotically with the host, and their presence is now recognized, thanks to numerous ultrahigh-throughput DNA sequencing techniques. The skin microbiome is comprised of microorganisms and it depends on host factors and the external factors which are as land, geographical location and certain other factors that regard to the lifestyle of an individual and the habits like feeding and grooming. Nevertheless, there are many publications that research how skin microbiome is involved in numerous body functions interconnected with skin: skin microbiome is essential for host defense against environmental challenges involving symbiotic and commensal interactions between organisms and host. In addition, the skin

microbiome plays a crucial role in shaping immune immunity and tolerance during the immune system regulation of microbial limit. The presence of a symbiotic interaction between the host and the skin microbiome has also been examined in numerous studies of various skin diseases, including atopic dermatitis. Based on these postulations, the skin barrier breakdown might open a window for allergens and microbial antigens to penetrate, which may well initiate and maintain chronic inflammation. On the other hand, there is another hypothesis suggesting that disruption and derangement of the skin microbial environment could lead to altered antigen-presenting cell attraction and activation that in turn sustained skin inflammation. Specifically, atopic dermatitis is associated with a shift in skin microbial profile, where the beneficial cutaneous commensals for example the staphylococcal *Staphylococcus* species, *Chryseobacterium* spp., and the *Streptococcus* genus are reduced quantitatively [5,23-26].

Functions and Importance

Protection of skin health through microbiome The enhancement of the immune response is one of the main challenges of microbial communities colonizing the skin. This is mainly achieved by preventing the entrance of pathogenic microbes and confining the immune reaction more significantly the inflammatory processes which are rather deleterious than beneficial. The microbiota promotes physical barrier through invoking the innate defense of skin with the invading foreign settlers. In fact, the skin immune system, well can be referred to as a vital as was the gut-associated lymphoid tissue, has developed a cutaneous immune system that is fetus- and newborn-adapted. This leads to bacterial modelling of the dermal immune system through stimulation of the skin's subcorneal desquamation. Micro-organisms are also indirectly pressing for the production of antimicrobial peptides and sBFAs, short chain non-saturate diverse molecular species, which modulate skin barrier homeostasis and repair. As such, the skin requires the microbiota to perform many molecular and cellular functions [27-28]. A dysbiosis of the microbiome is evident in several layers of skin physiology degradation. Molecules and cells involved in skin homeostasis maintenance inside skin or in blood, are present in temporarily or permanently changed form in pathological skin in comparison with healthy skin. As we said in the beginning of this article, general medicine and dermatology in particular goes with equal steps towards more individual kind of approach using all sorts of explorations. Until now, no clear functional element or molecule has simultaneously linked the microbial ecosystem and the analyzed diseased control of the patient instead of the constraints of the skin- and mucus-associated ecosystem disorders treated versus

the composed diseases: asthma, atopic dermatitis, obesity and inflammatory bowel disease. Whether the correlation between the host phenotype and the skin bacterial diversity is a two-factor useful for the organism is an open question [29-30].

Skin Tissue Types and Their Role in Atopic Dermatitis

The skin which is the biggest organ in the human body can be divided into three major connective tissue groups that play several roles in skin functioning. These components have a very important function in the skin: they're keeping its structure and functioning intact. First of all, I would like to describe the epidermis, which is the outermost layer of the skin. The epidermis is four layered but some sources divide it into five layers below the dermal dermis. These layers begin from the dead, cornifying keratinocytes of the stratum corneum up to the living basal layer of the stratum basale. The regeneration and the change of the mature cells that comprise these layers are intricate procedures that require precise patterns of actions to occur. A measure of the basal cells moved up and thus divide to give rise to new stem cells and these cells go up to the surface. These cells move from one location to another and as they do so they change their morphology and function before they become the flattened corneocytes of SC layer. This overlapping pattern of the epidermis gives both strength and flexibility toward outer layer of the skin. The major function of epidermal tissue is to form barrier between the internal and the external environment. This barrier provides the capacity to hold water and other essential nutrients exclusive of the rest of the organism even as it shields the latter against other unfriendly forces in its environment. The epidermal cells form a barrier thus protecting the tissues below from UV rays and hence lowers the onslaught of skin cancer illnesses. In addition, it acts as a barrier to prevent withstand invasion by microorganisms and other pathogens, lowers the chances of getting infected [31-34].

Proceeding to the dermis, the layer of skin found directly below the epidermis, we find a beehive of a cellular, fibrous, and matrix activity. The dermis includes fibroblasts, collagen fibers, blood vessels, nerves and the like and many other structural components. It is established that this connective tissue layer concerning strength and elasticity in regards to the skin. Collagen fibers combined with elastic fibers are the source of skin strength and elasticity. These fibers let the skin stretch and return to its original form and state without becoming weak. However, the dermis holds capillary-the blood that supplies the skin with nutrients and sense receptors-regulating touch, feeling of temperature and pain. Each of the components described here plays its part in the maintenance of homeostasis in the whole organism. [35-36].

Lastly, we reach the subcutaneous fat compartment, which resides beneath the dermis. This adipose connective tissue layer serves several important functions. Firstly, it acts as an energy reserve, providing a source of fuel during times of caloric deficit or increased energy requirements. Secondly, it serves as thermal insulation, helping to regulate body temperature by reducing heat loss. In addition, the subcutaneous fat layer also provides padding and protection to the underlying structures, reducing the risk of injury from external forces [37-38].

In summary, the skin is a complex and dynamic organ composed of three main connective tissue layers: the epidermis, dermis and the subcutaneous fat layer together. Every layer plays a role and is essential in the skin's function incorporating its main roles as a protective barrier, strength, flexibility and homeostasis. Knowledge of all these layers is vital for accurate appreciation of the skin's complications and significance as a single organ. The skin is also a network of connective tissues and, as the largest organ, strongly supports all the functions being attributed to it. The skin structure consists of the following major layers: epidermal layer, dermal layer and hypodermic layer each of which has specific functions in skin's barrier and physiological properties [39-40].

Beginning with the epidermis the outermost layer of skin it is made up of five layers that have functions that are unique to this part of the skin. These layers consist of the stratum corneum whose cells are cornified, dead keratinocytes to the living layer or the stratum basale. Both the renewal and differentiation processes within these layers call for a well-coordinated set of measures. Basal layer stem cells undergo cell division and the newly formed cells migrate upwards. These cells move and change their characteristics and become corneocytes which forms the outermost layer, known as the stratum corneum. This palisade like arrangement offers much needed rigidity as well as a certain degree of elasticity to the skin [41-42].

First and foremost, the derma's most vital function is to provide skin as a means of creating physical demarcation between the internal and the outside world. It confines water and vital nutrients within the body and at the same time protects it from hostile dangers. The epidermis protects the body against UV radiation and lower chances of developing skin cancer, as well as safeguard other tissues. Also, it also works as an insulator against other microorganisms as well as agents of infection, thereby reducing incidences of infections [19,43].

Turning now to the dermis, located just beneath the epidermis, we find a population of structures in constant activity. This includes fibroblasts, collagen fibers, blood vessels, nerves and many more. This layer gives support and withstand to the skin. These Kolagen

and elastic fibres provide skin strength as well as flexibility based on which the skin can be stretched without compromising on its structure. In addition, food and nutrient supply, and the skin's nerve endings for sensations of touch, temperature, and pain can all be found in the dermis, which contains blood capillaries. The dermis – in combination with these elements – plays a role in the regulation of homeostasis of the individual.

Last of all, the subcutaneous fat compartment is in the deeper layer of dermis. There are multiple roles for this adipose connective tissue layer. First of all, it is used as an energy store, that allows meeting our energy need during the periods of negative energy balance or when our energy demand is high. Second, it has thermal regulating properties by maintaining the body heat through prevention of heat conduction. Also, from an applied point of view of, the subcutaneous fat layer acts to protect the underlying structures from mechanical traumas.

To summarize, the skin is a complex and dynamic organ composed of three primary connective tissue layers: to the epidermal-dermal and dermal-subcutaneous fat layers. All the layers are largely involved in the skin functions of afford protection, strength, flexibility and homeostasis. Knowledge about each layer helps to realize the crucially important and highly diverse function of the skin as a whole.

In atopic dermatitis, substantial modifications have already been documented between the histological architecture and the biochemical milieu of the skin. In total, damage to the investing tissues of the epidermis, dermis, and subcutaneous tissue is one of the main causes of atopic dermatitis. The organization of healthy tissue defines the microenvironment that supports growth of cutaneous microbiota including densities of microbial families and abundance within specific cutaneous niches, distribution of different microbial families or genera or species. Tissue specific anatomical characteristics of skin can also dictate specific skin limited activated immune responses, including innate immune response succeeded by a cell mediated response that clearly shapes the skin associated microbiome. An absence of skin tissue structure may reduce the capacity for the adaptive immune response to protect against inflammation, increase infection and disease progression, although this has not previously been considered in atopic dermatitis studies. Nevertheless, the detailed involvement of skin tissues in the pathogenesis of atopic dermatitis opens first the possibility to stress the concept of early treatment of potential tissue defects and multifactorial approach to the management of atopic dermatitis with focus on support of skin microbiota and skin topography that may allow faster rehabilitation of patient. Altered immune status along with decreased levels of microbial

species competition and therefore, reduced microbiome richness has also been documented in challenges to the cutaneous microbiome in those with thin skin and/or an impaired skin barrier. In these people, skin communities may more easily transition to the alteration of the feature of dysbiosis than in people with healthy robust skin. Furthermore, the severity of the atopic dermatitis is related to both skin microbiota and microbiota and immunity. Microbiota expansion inhibition is also affected by the related systemic inflammation and exfoliative barrier and the inability of the mice to counterize the dysregulated microbiome invites new perspective [46-50].

Atopic Dermatitis Pathogenesis

Atopic dermatitis is a chronic relapsing eczematous skin disorder characterized by pruritus, and has a multifactorial etiology. Suggested contributing causes of atopic dermatitis are immune disorder and impaired skin barrier function. Atopic dermatitis immunopathological mechanisms are mainly characterised by an increased activity of T-helper type 2 (Th2) cells accompanied by production of numerous pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokines. As seen sometimes this results in inflammation in the skin and also sometimes the problem becomes systemic. This immune dysregulation is semi conditioned by the assess of allergens and semi conditioned by the systemic activities apropos the normal skin microbiome. Still, the complete nature of the onset and the course of atopic dermatitis development are not clear completely; however, it is understood that they depend on genes and various environmental factors. Significant involvement of microorganisms in the development of atopic dermatitis can be explained by the effectiveness of many antibiotics, antiviral preparations, and antifungal drugs for the treatment of the disease [5,51].

Patients with atopic dermatitis face a barrier dysfunction because there is a presentation of a dysfunctional protein filamentous structure in skin because filaggrin protein that protects skin from bacteria, viruses and allergens is cleaved. This cleavage is dependent on matrix metalloproteinases derived from keratinocytes and mast cells. Dry skin and lack of proper skin barrier in atopic dermatitis lead to microbial and viral penetration as well as inflammation. Somewhat surprisingly, the outer layer of the skin may play a more crucial role in the allergens' ability to penetrate the epidermis than microbes and viruses. But in practice, immune dysregulation and barrier dysfunction are not exactly separate and independent steps in skin disease pathogenesis, because inflammation can provoke filaggrin and filaggrin metabolism. Moreover, microbiota and viruses on the skin also may play a feedback in the regulation of immune response [52-53].

Immune Dysregulation

Atopic dermatitis arises from multiple interacted pathways, and for important diseases, dysregulation of the immune system plays a key role. There are also skin barrier impairments which cause patients of this disease to be more prone to allergens of both cutaneous and systemic types, colonization, skin infections and microbial infections. Both the branches of immunity are employed in the body's attempt to protect the skin. Keratinocytes evidently offer possessed and antimicrobial barrier, releasing house and antimicrobial allorines represented incalled cytokines and antimicrobial peptides required to pull and stimulate the innate immune cells type mast cells, eosinophils, and myeloid derived suppressor cells. Renewable changes in skin are the basis of the responses that define learning and anamnestic chronic outcomes. Concerning the relationship of the key actors of immune response the dendritic cells and $\gamma\delta$ T cells are implicated in the internalization of the antigens, T cell priming and the sustenance of the T cells in the skin. CD3 + T cell population is a large percentage of immune cells in affected skin [18, 54-56].

Th2 responses are considered to play a central role in the development of skin allergy in atopic dermatitis. Skin IgE, mast cell activation, and cytokines define a Th2 endophenotype. Some immune responses can promote homing and activation of the tissue's proper T lymphoid cells. Food and inhalant allergens, pathogen and size-associated microbes can stimulate a variety of antigen cells and incite an immune response. A change in the immune system is the main ruler that defines changes in the body in the formation of atopic dermatitis. These immune aspects were described in the initial case in addition to the IgE circulatory network and skin IgE autoantibodies that activate mast cells or basophils. During inflammation process, eosinophils, T cells, mast cells produce diverse cytokines that increase or decrease the inflammatory process and define the type of immune reaction. However, because chronic, there are several events leading to morbidity and comorbidities of systemic illness occurrences. There are diverse mechanisms and many components by which immune cells in the skin tissue communicate and stimulate inflammation. More rubbing and scratching will further damage the skin barrier as this continuous cycle of skin inflammation is created. The release of cytokines by immune cells results in an amplified response between the nerve cells or neurones and Langerhans and other dendritic cells. The number of saliva-active nerve endings is increased by the balance of parasympathetic responses to allergic inflammation in atopic dermatitis. These different avenues form the possible therapeutic targets which can be exploited to their full potential [57-60].

Barrier Dysfunction

Skin barrier dysfunction is included in the AD pathogenesis plan on its way to becoming the foundation of clinical understanding. The skin provides a barrier to physical, chemical, microbial, biologic stress and environmental conditions besides retaining water on the host's body. The breakdown of epidermal integrity could lead to TSW and epidermal barrier disorder or defective epidermal barrier. AC1 patient's have elevated TEWL scores above healthy skin; however, there is evidence of heterogeneous skin barrier dysfunction within the patient population. Various processes can contribute to barrier disruption – alteration of the lipid envelope on the epidermis outer layer, decreased synthesis of structural proteins owing to improper epidermisocyte maturation, dysregulation of some keratinocytes' proper functioning, and the decline or imbalance of the skin microbiome, leading to dermal inflammation. Preventing flare comprises rebuilding the skin barrier function since the barrier function and cutaneous immune responses are mutually intertwined to form a cycle when direct skin anti-inflame are used alone [61-63].

Once again, direct skin anti-inflammatory treatments require the barrier dysfunction to be addressed since it will continue to provide antigens for the ADS when the treatments wear off. However, in contrast to topicals, the primary objectives of systems are first to stop the cycle between inflammation and impaired skin barrier and second to decrease systemic inflammatory activity. The next thing will be to restore the barrier function at which oral or topical anti-inflammatory or even non-anti-inflammatory agents can be effected. This is not the first time treatments directly addressing the immune process produce minimal impacts on skin barrier. The presence of live bacteria in several prescription emollients re-iterating the principal of Charter change of the cutaneous microbiota to improve the skin barrier defect [64-67].

Skin Microbiome Dysbiosis in Atopic Dermatitis

The skin microbiome is a diverse and dense microbial community which plays important roles for skin homeostasis. As a result, it has been suggested that disruption of skin microbial homeostasis might be one of the factors aggravating and sustaining atopic dermatitis. If the balance of the members causing the change in the composition of the microbiome is disrupted, it will be referred to as dysbiosis. These changes increase, for example, the colonization of pathogens with the potential to cause additional inflammation – that may change the course of the disease to heavier and more resistant forms. The relationship between dysbiosis and atopic dermatitis severity is not clear: there are times when the severe types present increased bacterial load or the disease

varies in terms of microbial patterns in colonization, whether or not this is related to the deficit in antimicrobial function or if defective skin affiliation leads to microbial colonization that induces severe clinical signs [5,23].

Of course, it is at present evident that one of the key factors defining the maintenance of the disease is a certain bacterium. There are some microorganisms that have been described which aggravate atopic dermatitis symptoms: Some of the peptides synthesized by certain fungi are capable of stimulating inflammation and newly discovered density of certain bacteria in skin has recently been linked with severity of atopic dermatitis. Several works claim a connection between atopic dermatitis and having an abnormal microbial load – patients with more severe rashes have a three times increased microbial count, or are more likely to harbour certain pathogenic flora. However, the contribution of skin dysbiosis in atopic dermatitis is unknown and might affect profoundly such a connection between the existence or lack of certain microbial species and the phenotype atopic dermatitis patients. Dysbiosis might impair the skin barrier and upregulate the immune and inflammatory responses in atopic skin: certain enterotoxins directly stimulate keratinocytes and reduce the integrity of the skin barrier, whilst fractions of Gram-positive bacteria directly activate the skin innate response and inflammation. But dysbiosis might not only be a consequence but also a cause of the disease: The atopic dermatitis skin might have a different antibacterial host defence potential through secretion of antimicrobial peptides, sebaceous gland activity, and the content of salt in the sweat, and thus dysbiosis could be a consequence of the primary atopic dermatitis immune system dysregulation, decreased antimicrobial peptide production, and skin structure changes. It is a complex and fascinating area of research because in the case of a primary role of dysbiosis in atopic dermatitis, the microbiome could be a potential therapeutic target [23,68-70].

Altered Microbial Composition

The bacterial load by gene copy number is at least comparable or reduced on uninvolved AD skin compared with healthy skin but enhanced on chronic lesional skin. With regards to microbial diversity, self-sampling studies likewise report differences between AD status when compared to appropriately matched control groups, although at least two of these report more marked differences between AD and non-atopic versus non-lesional AD skin. Nevertheless, only two of these groups have provided evidence of microbial dysbiosis on lesional skin as compared to nonlesional skin in terms of bacterial richness and/or global brand. Several more recent investigations have tried to refine the description of the actual alterations of microbial

communities in AD. Low rates of bacterial culture conformity were identified in atopic persons and the lesion sites, but the overall microbial load intensified with the region's severity and the diversification level, however.

The majority of the presentation at latter skin microbial conference highlighted changes in the fatty acid composition or amount, enzyme activity, cellular infiltrate and/or antimicrobial peptide in skin bearing microbes in atopic compared to non-atopic skin. Often the answer to whether any findings were particular to lesional skin is contingent with the study since several of these alterations are also evidenced in non-lesional atopic skin in contrast to that of non-atopic persons. The literature originating from case control studies examining the impact of severity of atopic disease on microbial deference, specifically diversity has therefore been varying with two longitudinal studies showing no such association. A single paper demonstrated an association of bacterial richness with increase in the severity of disease in those patients, who have the highest disease severity. This question to indicate remains the biggest clinical unknown where, that discovery increased relative level of some bacteria with more severe disease however is not only very typical but, more informative reproducibility of that is between the different studies. tentatively, restoration of these particular bacteria is correlated with amelioration of disease severity scores in atopic infants [48,74,75].

Impact on Disease Severity

We are only now getting a clue on how a dysbiotic skin microbiome can contribute to symptom worsening of AD. Imbalance in the microbiome is said to trigger inflammation and worsen skin changes to affect the flare progression and the degree of skin inflammation. Abnormal bacterial colonization is rare in persons without filaggrin mutation and an intact skin surface lipid barrier. Methicilline resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* known to complicated the severe types of AD. There is a positive association of *Staphylococcus aureus* colony-forming units with the severity of the disease. This is an initial step of substantially changing the disease and the reported quality of life of a patient by the bacteria. Further rationale is given by the fact that patients' self-reported symptoms while reducing overtime are commensurate with the change of *Staphylococcus aureus* colony forming unit at six days post application of antibiotics. The overall rise in bacterial burden, *Staphylococcus aureus* in particular, is invariably mentioned; these changes are more often and pronounced in severe AD compared with mild AD patients. Thus, this is the second positive association which suggests that the degree of microbial load will affect the severity of a disease [76-79].

There is evidence which conclusively links AD exacerbations to alterations in skin microbiota. It is critical to note that disease flares occur in AD patients owing to results of specific environmental insults that may augment growth of potential skin pathogens. It is a current belief that restoration of a normal skin bacterial microbiota could minimize AD manifestations. On how this transpires as a mechanism, more research remains to be done. Reduction of inflammation was believed to occur due to the successful intervention on microbiome. Several clinical trials have shown a relationship between improved skin microbiome richness and client-rated quality of life markers. Also, it looks like patients themselves get benefits from higher levels of community richness and variety in sense of decreased symptoms. It helps in regaining skin health through this approach. This can be translated simply into increasing patient's engagement by enhancing a patient's well-being. Presumably, variable patients' phenotypes will favor particular living drugs addressed at the skin bona fide commensal. This is the third sign that this approach has extrinsic clinical relevance [49,80,81].

Therapeutic Interventions

Probiotics are beneficial as adjuvant therapies for almost all kinds of CRAD, but only the studies with selected probiotic strains demonstrate effectiveness. The circumstances that could yield to the best administration method should be defined, the patient group to which it is recommended, and the roles of the transgenerational transfer of microbiota should be highlighted. Prebiotics also have some potential as the adjunct therapy, although they have been investigated more extensively than probiotics. Randomized controlled trials have to be conducted in order to find out what local strains are better, as local strains might be likely to vary from person to person. Antimicrobial modulator/ topical microbiome therapy also would be helpful, as we learned that normal skin microbiota can enhance the skin barrier in atopic dermatitis. H2As and high dose antibiotics also show some effect in preventing atopic dermatitis but are not ready for clinical application. Summary: Manipulating the microbiome is a useful approach towards managing atopic dermatitis. A form of strain can exist in the clinical practice as the type of strain is known to vary with individuals hence one ways to prevent atopic dermatitis may be to intervene in the atopic dermatitis skin of mothers as well as infants. That is why targeting skin microbiota in AD could be appropriate as if the skin from a healthy adult will be sterilized and grafted to become AD skin it will develop AD. The expected outcomes include: Utilizing this paper, the treatment of skin dysbiosis needed to be compared with traditional treatment. More research needs to be conducted in order to see how successful this approach is. The

administration methods, the type of patient, and the transmission of microbiome from one generation to other also has to be determined. To the authors' knowledge, only two trials have been evidenced to demonstrate that a probiotic reduced the risk of atopic dermatitis relapse [82,84].

Probiotics and Prebiotics

Probiotics are defined as those microorganisms that aim at being administrated to the host in order to confer health benefits. They are proposed to ameliorate symptoms related to atopic dermatitis in several pathways: they modulate bacterial efficiency into the gut, and the human immune system, and the skin-gut axis as well as the microbial inhabitants in the skin. While Probiotics refers to friendly bacteria, prebiotics are not bacteria but a feed or fertilizer to healthy bacteria. Hence they support the healthy bacteria which could decrease the confusing bacteria in a manner to an extent. It is also possible to take to prevent skin dysbiosis and deal with the condition using pro- and prebiotics, which is a balance of skin microorganisms [85,86].

In the present review, the evidence in support of probiotics for AD has been systematically evaluated. As a co-intervention it is postulated that some evidence exists for using probiotics in order to alleviate the symptoms of atopic dermatitis and also decrease the reliance on steroids or calcineurin inhibitors. Similarly to the case reflected by gut microbiota, the skin microbiota may be influenced by probiotics. For instance, Lactobacillus, Bifidobacterium, and Streptococcus given orally reduced the SCORAD in comparison to placebo, the genetic testing results indicated skin colonization with Bifidobacterium spp. However, some research groups are studying the intent to use a probiotic to modify skin microbiota in AD adult and found that the probiotic introduced group had an increase in skin bifidobacteria and increase skin permeability [87,88].

Topical Microbiome Modulators

The practice of applying defined microbial species locally to alter the microbiome of specific skin has been a promising concept shifting from agricultural science to skin care. These modulators are expected to be in dermocosmetics and are to be used by consumers in making their own skin healthier. The idea is that use of these formulations every day will make an ongoing impact on the skin's microbial ecosystem and enhance the function of the skin's micro barrier. The herd available up till present are basic suspension of single or number of live bacterial strain in basic protein vehicle or saline or live bacteria in fat or other lipids. Alternatively, the bacteria are encapsulated in silica, spores BO or bio-cellulose discs or in a conditioned media. A theory being that substances released by growing bacteria enhance the growth of [67,89,90].

Conclusion and Future Directions

In summary, many lines of evidence point to an inextricable association between host immune dysregulation, barrier dysfunction, and the skin microbiome in atopic dermatitis. Biological pathways described in transcriptomics or proteomics are significantly shared with pathways dysregulated in genes directly involved in host-microbe or microbe-microbe interactions, suggesting that dysregulated immune cross-talk can have unintended microbiome-altering effects and vice versa. An altered immune-microbiome axis in atopic dermatitis has profound impacts on clinical practice, where the emergence of microbiome-targeting therapies could well represent the beginnings of personalized medicine for one of the most important chronic healthcare burdens in the developed world. However, clinicians and investigators face critical questions: whether the cutaneous dysbiosis evident in atopic dermatitis constitutes a causative association with the development of skin inflammation; the long-term efficacy and safety of rebuilding a normal skin microbiome; and what the new frontier of host-microbiome and microbe-microbe functional interactions will unlock as the immune system is reprogrammed over time. Exploring common mechanisms of host-microbiome-microbiome interactions in skin disease through characterization of microbial systems biology of pathogenesis will become an important future research direction. Moving towards reshaping the skin microbiome to prevent or treat disease necessitates the development of a greater understanding of the principles underpinning new interactions between microbial partners. Studies that focus on non-bacterial players in eczema are insufficiently understood, and indeed, the roles and functional interactions between known and anonymous microbes in atopic dermatitis pathogenesis deserve increased exploration at the genetic, functional, and ecological level. New and under-researched model systems are essential. At the time of writing, the pipeline of clinical trials is primed to explode. While pivotal open questions may necessitate clinical largesse, no one in the field of allergy, immunology, dermatology, or microbiology can be anything but optimistic for the translational fruits yet to be reaped in treating an epidemic through skin microbial solutions.

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